

GR4FITE3

**Graphite resilience for
lithium-ion battery anodes
via sustainable European
end-to-end supply chain**

Funded by the
European Union

What is GR4FITE3 about?

Graphite resilience for lithium-ion battery anodes:

- A **whole new supply chain** to achieve a more efficient production of lithium-ion batteries in Europe.
- A **novel silicon-based composites** made from natural and recycled graphite materials.

GR4FITE3 will lead to the development and commercialisation in Europe of **more sustainable, improved batteries** for use in **electric vehicles** and **energy storage** applications for **solar and wind facilities**.

Keep up with the project

 GR4FITE3 project

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